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Examining safe urban mobility for the improved welfare and wellbeing of older people in smart cities

Bokolo Anthony Jnr^{a,b}

^aDepartment of Applied Data Science, Institute for Energy Technology, Halden, Norway; ^bDepartment of Computer Science and Communication, Østfold University College, Halden, Norway

ABSTRACT

One aspect of older people that has received little consideration is the mobility safety challenge faced by older people. Therefore, municipalities are still faced with limitations in understanding the mobility safety demands of older people, both those with and without disabilities, in society. An important goal is to provide mobility safety for older people. Therefore, the aim of this study is to examine the use of emerging technologies and universal design measures to improve the safe walkability and wayfinding of older people. Data were collected from the literature subsequently, meta-analysis and qualitative content analysis were employed to present the findings from the secondary sources. This review study contributes to the body of knowledge by exploring how universal design measures and the use of emerging technologies can promote safe mobility for the improved welfare and well-being of older people towards secure, independent living and societal participation in smart cities. More importantly, this article provides implications for the re-design and development of safe walkability and wayfinding requirements for older people in smart cities. Furthermore, this study reviews older people's safety requirements in public transportation, mobility safety behaviour and measures to mitigate risks faced during walking, which is lacking in the literature. Finally, recommendations are provided to support older people's mobility by suggesting the adoption of emerging technologies, such as assistive devices, routeing and navigation tools.

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KEYWORDS

Safe urban mobility; safe walkability and wayfinding; mobility accessible; welfare and well-being; older people; smart cities

Highlights

- Examine the use of emerging technologies to improve safe walkability and wayfinding of older people.
- Contributes to promote secure, independent living, and societal participation in smart cities.

CONTACT Bokolo Anthony Jnr Department of Applied Data Science, Institute for Energy Technology, Os Alle 5, Halden 1777, Norway; Department of Computer Science and Communication, Østfold University College, Halden, Norway

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- Facilities the re-design and development of safe walkability and wayfinding requirements for older people.
- Employs universal design measures to improve safe mobility of older people in public transportation.
- Support older people's mobility in the use of assistive devices, routing applications, and navigation tools.

1. Introduction

It is predicted that about 25% of the population will have reached the age of about 65–67 years by 2050 (Levin et al., 2012). This change will involve from '65–74' to the oldest old '75 and older', especially those over 80 years who will need mobility support. To this end, measures to promote mobility of older people will be progressively important in the future (Hjorthol, 2013; Bokolo, 2023b). Mobility is important to carry out daily activities and to maintain autonomy, a healthy psychological outlook, independence and quality of life (including psychological well-being, physical health, access to support services and community and overall life satisfaction). Older people rely on access to a vehicle either as a driver or a passenger for their mobility needs (Oxley et al., 2010). The mobility and the ability of older people to get out of their homes are important for their welfare, well-being and quality of life (Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017). Being unable to drive or not being provided with mobility means as a passenger is one of the causes of depression among older people. Moreover, older people's ability to freely access and use the public transportation system has long been identified as one of the seven significant components in the Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL) (Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017).

Hence, in an ageing society, urban mobility decisions should be based on forward-looking and improving the quality of life of the citizens (especially vulnerable road users such as older people), in the society the goal of municipalities should be to improve their present and future social and physical infrastructure investments. This will prepare cities and communities for an equal, inclusive, safer and more equitable environment (Mercado et al., 2010). Therefore, the availability of different mobility means will help the older population to have a sense of being empowered in old age towards independent living (Hjorthol et al., 2010; Levin et al., 2012). The findings from a survey in the United Kingdom (UK) suggested that the number of trips embarked by older people increased by 12–19 per cent and the distance travelled also increased to 40–45 per cent, respectively throughout 15 years between 1985 and 1998, with 27 per cent increase for travel distance within the same period. The result highlighted that the provision of improved urban mobility access was associated with the increase in social participation and mobility, and this also contributed to improved quality of life (Sze & Christensen, 2017). One characteristic of population ageing that has received quite little consideration is the daily mobility of the ageing population is the use of public transportation (Jnr, 2025).

Thus, mobility and ageing have some significant societal implications. This is because mobility is directly connected with the health, welfare and well-being of older people (Hjorthol et al., 2010). However, only a few studies have explored the impact of assistive technology on the welfare and well-being and in relation to older people's access to public

transportation as related to walkability and wayfinding (Hjorthol, 2013; Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017). Also, there is little up-to-date, comparable knowledge and representation regarding how emerging technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based Machine Learning (ML), are being used for the safe mobility of older people (Bokolo, 2023b). Furthermore, it is not always clear what measures can be employed to increase older people's use of these AI technologies in public transportation, i.e. to improve safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding (Jnr, 2025). Nevertheless, the question of how to improve the well-being and welfare of older people through mobility is a complex societal and policy issue. As with old age, an individual's functional abilities as well as social demands change, hence certainly influencing mobility mode, travel needs and travel options (Siren et al., 2015; Sze & Christensen, 2017). Therefore, this study aims to examine the following research questions.

- What is the state-of-the-art in regard to safe walkability and wayfinding for older people?
- How can the use of assistive technology models and universal design measures help improve safe urban mobility for older people?
- How can the use of emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based Machine Learning (ML) improve safe walkability and wayfinding for older people?

To address the above research questions, this study contributes to the body of knowledge by employing a structured literature review to examine the use of universal design measures and emerging technologies to improve the safe walkability and wayfinding of older people. The findings provide a better understanding of the mobility situation of older people within the age of 65–74, 75 and older and the relationship between urban mobility services and aspects of welfare and well-being. Accordingly, the novelty of this study is based on the designed model, grounded on the Human Activity Assistive Technology (HAAT) model and universal design measures employed to improve safe urban mobility for older people. Evidence from this study provides *best practices*, including guides for urban planners, municipality administration and decision-makers for achieving safe urban mobility for the better welfare and well-being of older people. More importantly, the finding from this study promotes mobility accessibility for older people by the use of emerging technologies, such as machine learning-based solutions (for personalized walkability and wayfinding guidance tools, street/pedestrian crossing aids) that can help older pedestrians with and without disabilities to commute safely. The structure of the study is organized as follows: Section 2 is the literature review; Section 3 describes the methodology; Section 4 presents the findings; Section 5 introduces the discussion and implications. Section 6 provides the conclusion.

2. Literature review

Over the decade, a few studies have examined older people's use of public transportation. Among these studies, Vijaya Prakash and Taduri (2020) examined the safe navigation of older people and visually impaired persons, employing adhesive tactile walking surface indicators in the living environment. Somenahalli et al. (2016) explored accessible mobility and transportation issues of older people in relation to Australia and Japan. The study employed surveys and in-depth discussions in Australia and Japan and highlighted

accessible mobility and transportation challenges in Australia's ageing society by providing evidence on some of the important laws and policies prevailing in Japan. Tournier et al. (2016) studied mobility and safety issues among older pedestrians. Their study presented current knowledge of older-adult challenges and the key components of pedestrian movement, i.e. wayfinding, walking, road crossing and obstacle negotiation. Krogstad et al. (2015) examined how to improve walking for older adults. The authors focused on assessing the physical, individual and social factors and the effect on older groups' perception towards walking in Norway. Siren et al. (2015) researched well-being and out-of-home activities among older persons residing with mobility impediments. The study focused on how discretionary and utilitarian activities across different types of out-of-home activities, thus contributing to the well-being of older people aged 80–95 in Denmark.

Additionally, Hjorthol (2013) investigated how transport resources are allocated among diverse groups of older people. The study also evaluated to what extent the transport needs of older people are met and how this is correlated to their well-being in Norway. Schlieder et al. (2013) examined the deployment of assistive technology to facilitate the mobility of senior citizens. The author aimed to address mobility barriers and establish a mobility chain via social collaboration by a Geo-Wiki that offers alternative routes, as well as a matchmaking service linking older people with potential volunteers. Levin et al. (2012) conducted a literature review and provided measures as best practices to improve mobility among older people in Scandinavian settings. The findings from the study suggested strategies for improving public transport concerns in relation to the mobility needs of future older people. Banister and Bowling (2004) explored the quality of life for older people as related to the transport factor. The study addresses the concept of quality of life to understand and improve older people's quality of life as related to the locality, mobility patterns and social networks. Oxley et al. (2010) explored safe mobility among older drivers and further identified the challenges faced by urban road designers.

Although obstacles associated with public transportation have widely been investigated in the literature, there are limited studies that examine the interaction of older people, such as transfer time (walking and waiting), in a multimodal and intermodal mobility setting. These multimodal and intermodal mobility systems support older people to make seamless mobility transfers when they commute to reach their destinations (Muñoz et al., 2016). Besides, older people are not provided with direct routes when they commute, and this mostly hinders their mobility safety when they use public transportation. Moreover, fewer studies provide an integrated multimodality and intermodality navigation approach, including data on walkability (accessible and accessibility transport) and wayfinding (navigation support) (Muñoz et al., 2016). Therefore, this review study contributes to providing an understanding of how to improve older people's safe use of public transportation. The findings will assist municipalities, transport planners and urban designers to adopt emerging technologies such as AI-based ML to improve safe walkability and wayfinding for older people. Also, this study will explore the use of assistive technology models and universal design measures to improve the safe urban mobility for older people, thereby, providing guides on how to design integrated mobility services required by older people, especially those with disabilities, towards improving their welfare and well-being.

3. Methodology

In this study, a structured literature review was performed to synthesize the existing body of research and opted to use Scopus and Web of Science databases, as these online libraries provide an extensive source for high-quality peer-reviewed scholarly journal articles, conference proceedings, book chapters and books. In conducting the structured literature review, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were specified to guide the selection of sources (Fink, 2019; Kitchenham & Charters, 2007; Lindkvist & Melander, 2022). The scope of this study is more aligned to the literature, investigating safe and sustainable urban mobility, the use of emerging technologies and universal design measures to improve the safe walkability and wayfinding of older people, including the welfare and well-being in smart cities. Hence, a structured keyword search was performed on titles, abstracts and keywords from the selected online database. Different sets of keywords were employed for the searches: 'safe mobility for older people' or 'mobility for older people' or 'senior citizens mobility' and 'mobility accessibility' and 'older people mobility *' and 'aging*', and 'smart cities' or 'mobility welfare' and 'walkability*' and 'wayfinding*' and 'public transportation' and 'sustainable public transportation' and 'emerging technologies' and 'digital technologies'. The search was limited to only journal articles, conference proceedings, book chapters and technical reports written in English. [Figure 1](#) depicts the literature search process.

The searches resulted in 157 papers respectively, as only a few studies have focused on safe and sustainable mobility and walkability of older people. Next, 12 papers were removed as duplicates, resulting in 145 sources. The titles and respective abstracts were briefly read to validate the content of the articles, as such, 88 papers were eliminated as they did not have a clear focus on safe urban mobility, walkability and wayfinding of older people or welfare and well-being of older people or use of a design method and/or emerging technologies for the mobility of older people. Thereafter, the remaining 57 articles were completely read. Furthermore, to improve the literature review, a snowballing approach was employed based on some references identified from our initially selected sources. That procedure yielded an additional 9 sources (Anthony Jnr, 2024; Bokolo, 2023a; Jnr, 2025; Ruter, 2017; Solvoll, 2010; Sparelabs, 2019; United Nations, 2012; World Health Organization, 2002; World Health Organization, 2011), related to safe urban mobility of older people resulting to a total of 66 articles in the review. Thus, 66 sources were employed to examine the research questions posited in this study. [Figure 1](#) shows the process of the literature search employed. Then, secondary data were extracted from the literature and document reports, based on the research questions specified in the introduction section of this paper. Meta-analysis and qualitative data analysis were then employed, as suggested in the literature (Bokolo, 2023a; Jnr, 2025; Lindkvist & Melander, 2022; Miles and Huberman, 1984).

4. Findings

4.1. Meta-analysis of secondary data

In this section, a meta-analysis is carried out by analysing the secondary data based on the sources, year of publication, country of the publishing organization/institution, methods employed, and studied research areas related to the use of emerging

Figure 1. Literature review search process.

technologies and universal design measures for safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding of older people. **Figure 2** reveals that the majority of the included sources were published in 2020, with $N = 8$, followed by 2010 and 2021, with $N = 6$ sources. In 2011, 2015 and 2022, $N = 5$ sources were published related to the study area, respectively. In 2017 and 2019, recorded $N = 4$ sources. 2003 and 2016 had $N = 3$ sources and 2012, 2013, 2023 and 2024 had $N = 2$ sources. In conclusion, $N = 1$ was included from 1975, 1995, 2000, 2001, 2003, 2004, 2007, 2008 and 2014. This finding indicates that only a few studies have been published in the research area related to the use of emerging technologies and universal design measures to improve the safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding of older people. Thus, there is a need for this research study.

Figure 3 indicates that in analysing the selected 66 sources, most of the sources included in this study adopted literature review as the preferred methodology in their research, with 36 sources, followed by survey with 8 sources and interviews with 7 sources. **Figure 3** depicts other methods employed, such as case study by interview, case studies, experiments, focus groups and interviews and diary completion. The other remaining sources employed literature review & survey, literature review & conceptual, prototype & simulation, questionnaires and recorded injuries data, as shown in **Figure 3**. Finally, a few of the sources employed survey & focus group, survey, participatory observation & workshop, and workshops & interviews. This finding suggests that the use of emerging technologies and universal design measures to improve the

Figure 2. Distribution of selected sources by year.

safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding of older people is still an emerging research area; thus, there is a need for more empirical-based studies.

Figure 4 shows the countries where the authors of the sourced documents employed in this review study were published. The result depicts that a total of 27 countries, including 2 sources from the United Nations, were included. The results further suggest that most contributors to the study area of improving safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding of

Figure 3. Distribution of employed methodologies.

older people via the use of emerging technologies and universal design measures across different areas are published in Norway, Sweden and the United Kingdom, compared to other regions, as shown in Figure 4. Furthermore, out of the 66 sources included in this review study, Figure 5 outlines the main area that was examined in the selected sources. Figure 5 indicates that most of the studies investigated mobility and disabled people, sustainable transportation, mobility and accessibility, safe mobility of older people and general mobility compared to other areas investigated. However, only a few studies have examined the use of emerging technologies and universal design measures to improve the safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding of older people.

4.2. Qualitative data analysis of secondary data

4.2.1. Safe urban mobility needs for age-friendly city

According to ‘Erik Allardt’ Allardt (1975), welfare or well-being is defined as the satisfaction of needs associated with the three main aspects of life i.e. loving, having and being. The ability to use public transportation independently and autonomously facilitates social interactions. But older people between the ages of 65–74 and 75 and older are often considered to be a homogenous group in society in terms of their mobility accessibility needs (Bokolo, 2023b). This is due to greater differences within these groups when we consider different age, culture and especially for older people with disabilities (Alsnih & Hensher, 2003). Thus, older people with disabilities such as wheelchair users, those with hearing impairment, visual impairment and others with sensory and learning impairment, face many obstacles when walking and navigating. This prevents older people from fully participating in social activities and exercising their rights (Wazani et al., 2021).

The mobility of older people starts with the availability of information, as sufficient information is needed to make informed decisions for older people, whether they will travel using public transportation or if they will use alternative modes such as shuttle services, shared mobility services, etc. (Park & Chowdhury, 2022). Information on the provision of timetabled public transportation and fixed-route public transportation (Alsnih

Figure 4. Distribution of the country of selected sources.

Figure 5. Distribution of explored context in selected sources.

& Hensher, 2003). To improve the welfare or well-being of older people, there is a need to focus on mobility, accessibility and availability by including public transportation alternatives that offer a sense of security and independence, which help older people to have a sense of dignity (Alsnih & Hensher, 2003). But presently, there are inadequate public transportation alternatives for older people mostly partly due to the lack of understanding of the mobility needs of older people in society.

An age-friendly environment is dependent on the physical environment and the degree to which it enables walkability, wayfinding and mobility (Bokolo, 2023b). According to WHO, an age-friendly city is an urban environment that promotes the welfare, well-being and participation of all inhabitants irrespective of their age (World Health Organization, 2002). These include the provision of inclusive, equitable, accessible, safe and secure public transportation (Levin et al., 2012). The daily mobility patterns of older people vary and are suggestible to changes due to various factors, such as changes in older people's economy, physical and health or major life events, such as loss of a driving license, absent of a spouse or a partner, retirement, divorce or residing in a care home (Salmela et al., 2020). An age-friendly environment decreases the risk of falls and prevents the neglect of older people by increasing their safety within the environment as well as the security and protection of older people across the local community (Musselwhite & Haddad, 2010). Accordingly, age-friendly cities reduce inequities, protect and promote older people's inclusion and their ability to participate in society. An age-friendly city should promote pedestrian walking and convenient use of public transportation for all, regardless of gender, age, ethnicity or cultural background and health status (Metz, 2000).

Older people may face discrimination and negative attitudes based on their age. Creating an age-friendly environment fights ageism, promotes diversity and ensures that older people have the opportunity to fully participate in the local community (Salmela et al., 2020). To achieve an age-friendly city, municipalities should provide affordable public transportation for older people, create accessible and barrier-free public spaces that enable older people to maintain their independence and autonomy (Sze & Christensen, 2017). Moreover, by associating age-friendliness and sustainable travel modes, such as the use of public transportation, cycling and walking, municipalities can tackle the increase of CO₂ emissions and provide green mobility solutions to the ageing populations (Anthony Jnr et al., 2020). Metz (2000) suggested that the *mobility needs can be categorized into five areas*, ranging from daily travel, which is needed by older people to gain access to different places and people; psychological welfare and well-being of older people, which benefits movement such as getting out of their home and about the city.

The third area comprises *walking around the city as a form of exercise*; as well as *older people's involvement in the local community activities* and lastly their potential need for travel, which includes *knowing that a journey can be made by older people even if not essentially undertaken*. On the other hand, Musselwhite and Haddad (2010) proposed three categories of mobility needs, which include the primary, secondary and tertiary needs. The primary travel is linked to utilitarian needs (such as access to shops), whereas the secondary travel needs are mainly associated with affective mobility needs (such as control, autonomy and independence) and tertiary travel is associated with aesthetic needs (such as mobility travel). The main mobility needs for older people in smart cities are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6 depicts that the main mobility needs for older people towards achieving an age-friendly city are discussed below.

4.2.1.1. Accessibility. The public transportation system should enable older people to fulfil their mobility needs, e.g. the public transportation system should be accessible to older commuters digitally and physically. Various physical or digital barriers may significantly decrease the willingness of older persons to utilize a particular public transportation mode (Bokolo, 2023b). Physical accessibility barriers occur during the entire journey chain; for example, inaccessible buses or bus stops, long waiting times, health-related barriers or challenges in standing in a moving bus (Metz, 2000). Physical accessibility can be improved via the provision of more accessible facilities such as public stops, stations, environmentally-friendly vehicles and more inter-city routes. Public stops and stations should be built to include benches and well-lit shelters. Moreover, accessible pedestrian footpaths, ramps and kerbs should be provided and the removal of obstacles in the walking paths. Low-floor buses equipped with ramps should be provided (Salmela et al., 2020).

Digital barriers may be related to challenges faced by older people in finding travel information online, for instance, related to timetables, ticketing options, wayfinding (location finding via maps and identification of directions both on-board and at stops) (Jnr, 2025). Digital barriers also involve the limited awareness related to diverse transport options and the difficulties faced by older people in using mobile apps (Sze & Christensen, 2017). Assisted technologies and on-board facilities should be provided as appropriate. Travel timetables and other important information should be plainly understandable and visible throughout the journey, as older people need clear travel information due to their mental and physical conditions. For instance, older people may require extra information, such as payment options, accessibility of low-floor buses or the location of lifts at multi-floor stations. But to improve digital accessibility, there is a need to provide online courses for older people on how to use the internet to gather information about public transportation services, how to purchase tickets and make travel reservations (Jnr, 2025).

Figure 6. Mobility needs for older people in smart cities.

4.2.1.2. Availability. The public transportation system should be available based on a pre-defined time and route to older people. Thus, public transportation such as the local bus lines should cover routes with important service hubs (e.g. grocery shops, pharmacies, health centres, hospitals, etc.), else older people will use other mobility modes. Most cities provide flexible transport solutions which offer custom mobility services, such as taxis, to facilitate the mobility of older people (Bokolo, 2023b). These flexible transport solutions vary from shared cars, on-demand responsive buses, taxis, dedicated services, or community transport. Overall, the availability of information on possible mobility alternatives should be delivered transparently to older people to avoid presumptive and negative attitudes towards the acceptance and use of these mobility services (Anthony Jnr, 2020). Accordingly, barriers related to the availability of services to be addressed include inconsistent timetables, inadequate route connectivity or coverage with other public transportation modes, and inaccuracy or unreliability of mobility services (Salmela et al., 2020).

4.2.1.3. Acceptability. A public transportation system provided by the municipality should be a travel mode that older people are willing or intend to use; for example, it should be comfortable, safe and user-friendly. Acceptability includes the perception or preferences older people may have to a particular public transportation mode as related to the special mobility needs and requirements of older people (Gim, 2022). Possible barriers associated with the mobility acceptability often involve psycho-social factors, such as older people's attitude towards the use of public transportation or inherent habits towards personal car use (Anthony Jnr, 2022). These barriers may be linked to the lack of public safety, discomfort, poor service, general low quality and unhospitable behaviour of bus drivers towards older people. This may also be linked to negative attitudes of other passengers/commuters, pedestrians and cyclists (Salmela et al., 2020).

4.2.1.4. Affordability. This ensures that the public transportation system is viable within the financial capability of older people. This is because if any public transportation mode is too expensive, older people will certainly not use such a mode of travel, as most older people have lower income in retirement (Cui et al., 2017). As such, most municipalities provide subsidized schemes with discounted or lower fares to older people. Plausible barriers related to the affordability of public transportation services include expensive tickets or limited age-related incentives (Salmela et al., 2020).

4.2.2. Safe and accessible walkability for older people in smart cities

The evolution of smart cities of the twenty-first century aims to increase mobility, accessibility and walkability in urban spaces by promoting different modes of public transportation. It depends on the urban land use (e.g. nearness of different destinations) and the public transportation system (e.g. easiness to reach different mobility modes) (Kenyon et al., 2002). Accessibility is also related to the removal of barriers that limit movement across and within smart cities and the compliance of facilities and infrastructures to design standards (Mercado et al., 2010). The development of smart cities and related public infrastructure needs to be thoroughly assessed from the point of view of the removal of architectural barriers that guarantee mobility access. Moreover, in smart cities, it is important to assess how the built environment is safe and secure to walk,

specifically in the case of older people with disabilities (Campisi et al., 2021). Therefore, this section discusses walkability or walking accessibility. In particular, daily walking has substantial health benefits for older people (Krogstad et al., 2015). Walking is also considered an environmentally-friendly mode of public transportation (Levin et al., 2012). *Although the absence or inadequate supply of public transportation services is often highlighted as a reason for the lack of inclusion for older people with disabilities. Also, there are still few research that explored walkability and wayfinding issues related to the mobility accessibility of older people* (Campisi et al., 2021).

Walking is the most frequent and easy way to move, frequently acting as a complement to other public transportation modes for inter-modality (Campisi et al., 2021), thus walking is one of the most crucial travel modes (Levin et al., 2012). In European countries, 30-50% of older people commute on foot. Mostly, older people continually feel that accessibility of the pedestrian areas is poorly built, which results in difficulty when they move around their neighbourhood (Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017). Falls and injuries during walking are often caused indirectly or directly by obstacles in the surroundings; therefore, safety is an influential characteristic of older people's movements outside their residence (OECD, 2001). A study from *Sweden* revealed that injuries and falls among older people, as bicyclists and pedestrians, account for over three-fourths of traffic-related injuries encompassing older people. Over 60% of all injuries and falls outside the home of older people are regard as caused by injuries involving unaccompanied older pedestrians (Elvik & Bjørnskau, 2019; Levin et al., 2012). According to Levin et al. (2012), falls among older people walking alone are frequently caused by issues that have been determined as environmental, although in some cases, the health condition is a contributing factor.

In a review and analysis of injury statistics that occurred in *Norway*, it was revealed that older pedestrians are part of a disadvantaged group of road users as they are vulnerable to injury and are more prone to risk of falls (Elvik & Bjørnskau, 2019). They are mostly faced with long-lasting and more serious impairments when injured, including reduced quality of life and life expectancy. Thus, mobility, walkability and safety are closely related. A report in *Denmark* disclose similar results, highlighting that older people prefer cities with public transportation facilities, such as signal-regulated intersections, pedestrian crossings and cycle paths separated from streets and pavements, and to a largely feel unsafe when crossing the pedestrian road where these public facilities are not provided (Elvik & Bjørnskau, 2019). Furthermore, older pedestrians agreed that the provision of pavements is very important to ensure safe walkability and will opt to walk towards a pedestrian crossing compared to just crossing to the nearest point due to perceived safety issues (Levin et al., 2012). Additionally, in *Norway* 'the Norwegian Directorate of Health' recommended older people to be physically active with moderate intensity of about 150 min per week, which is equivalent to a 20-minute daily walk.

Moreover, in 2012, a national strategy to promote walking was introduced in *Norway*, aimed at making walking easier and more attractive means of transport (Krogstad et al., 2015). Furthermore, the Norwegian Public Roads Administration (Statens Vegvesen) proposed a national walking strategy (Berge et al., 2011), which aimed at promoting walking in smart cities, as a source of physical activity which contributes to good health. The National Transport Plan was carried out from 2014 to 2023 and it focused on making walking a more attractive mode of commuting. The walking strategy is in

line with the strategy of universal design, which is adopted in *Norway* to design public spaces (Levin et al., 2012). The increasing population necessitates the need for a policy to address public transportation needs in the future, and walking is considered a sustainable and healthy mode for humans and for the environment. It is anticipated that in the future about 68% of the public transportation in smart cities will be in the form of walking (Park & Chowdhury, 2022). As such, there is a need for walking campaigns/awareness and re-design of compactly built-up areas to be implemented. Public transportation services and bus stops/stations situated in compactly built-up areas will be positioned within walking distances and the neighbourhoods of inhabited areas will be designed to be more attractive for older pedestrians (Levin et al., 2012). The barriers that limit walkability of older people in smart cities comprise three main obstacles, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 depicts a summary of the main obstacles that impact the walkability of older people in smart cities. In smart cities, cycling and walking are sustainable travel modes as they bring environmentally-friendly and health benefits (Anthony Jnr, 2020). Walking is also seen as one of the easiest and quickest ways to get from one location to another. Thus, the fear of falling faced by older people is associated with these aforementioned barriers. As such, falls and injuries certainly pose a significant risk for older people (Salmela et al., 2020). With sustainable urban planning and re-design, the recognized barriers that limit walkability can be addressed to make walking safer and easier for older people (Krogstad et al., 2015; Salmela et al., 2020).

4.2.3. Measures to improve walkability of older people in smart cities

Walking is important for getting to local services and facilities and gaining access to public transportation. Thus, it is necessary to provide mobility and walkability safety to older people, where mobility safety is a state in which risky and hazardous conditions which can lead to injuries and falls are mitigated in smart cities (Levin et al., 2012). Safety is interlinked with injuries and falls. Injuries refer to the health results of a traumatic

Figure 7. Barriers that limit the walkability of older people in smart cities.

incident. Injuries are uncontrolled, unplanned events that can result in falls (Marin-Lamellet, 2011; Wretstrand & Marin-Lamellet, 2011). One study identified different walkability needs of older people as presented below.

- Separate lanes for cyclists, walking and pedestrians. Improved walking conditions by clearing walkway surfaces to reduce the slipping of pedestrian's especially in the winter season. Also, better handling of slippery environments and snow clearance, level surfaces on pavements and removal of hedges (Siren et al., 2015).
- Moreover, the provision of benches adjacent to footways/pavements as places to rest on, provision of wider pavements, bright street lighting along passages and footways, provision of safe crossing points with protection from fast-moving traffic and extended green times (Banister & Bowling, 2004).
- Safe paths for vulnerable road users, a road division for pedestrians and mopedists/bicyclists and a situation not too far away from the walkway. As well as fewer slopes at the point where pavement intersects with the removal of leaves and sweeping (Levin et al., 2012).
- Clean, smoother, wider footways/pavements in summer (e.g. litter and leaves) and winter (e.g. ice and snow). Also, the provision of clear information to bicyclists regarding traffic rules and behaviours in traffic prone areas (Krogstad et al., 2015; Levin et al., 2012).
- Accessible and available public transportation facilities and services are limited when the walking distance is quite long, and the municipality's provision of one-way streets.
- Limited steep footpaths can be an issue for older people when they are walking uphill on steep walkways (Levin et al., 2012). Lower curbs/pavements at pedestrian crossings with available benches adjacent to curbs situated near pavements with frequent sanding of pavements (Krogstad et al., 2015).
- An improved walking environment could enhance the perceived safety level for older people and individuals with disabilities. A smooth, solid and clear pavement separation between cycle path and footpath, improved pavement surface and a lower speed limit were found to be necessary for older people who rely on walking (Levin et al., 2012; Sze & Christensen, 2017).
- Provision of longer green light duration at older pedestrian crossings. As well as better signposts, signal regulations and better-built pedestrian crossings (Krogstad et al., 2015).
- Reduction of car traffic, reduced speed limits for cars and speed limits to 30 km/h, provide more bus stops, built bevelled which soften the edges of pavement structure for safety edges at pedestrian crossings and other strategic locations (Krogstad et al., 2015; Levin et al., 2012).

These measures mentioned above can improve older people's perceptions of risk, safety and vulnerability. Findings from Sze and Christensen (2017) suggested that the provision of pre-trip planning information on available public transportation (bus, taxi, train, tram, etc.), easy-to-access geospatial information of available transport service facilities, and pictures illustrating potential physical obstacles were identified as valuable, especially for older people with reduced independence. Moreover, during the winter season, it is especially challenging for older people due to difficulties in moving

and associated physical barriers. Krogstad et al. (2015) provided insights into walkability issues, such as inadequate winter maintenance faced by older people. Further findings from the study revealed that older people felt insecure in icy or slippery conditions and were at risk of falling and injuring themselves. Moreover, lumps of ice made the curbs uneven and bumpy and challenging for older people using a rollator walker or electric mobility; as such, some older people adapt by not going out at all.

4.2.4. Universal design to improve mobility safety and accessibility

The preservation of independent mobility for older people is in line with the ambition of Active Ageing as stipulated by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2002). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) implemented by the UN (United Nations, 2012) advocate for inclusive urban development, address equity, equality and further promote the welfare and well-being of all people regardless of their age, among several other goals. Based on the SDGs, transportation is necessary to address the needs of older persons, especially those with different abilities. The concept of Universal Design (UD) was invented by the architect Ronald Mace, who described it as the design of products and the environment that is usable by all to the greatest possible extent, without requiring specialized design or adaptation (Center for Universal Design, 1995; Sze & Christensen, 2017). Early efforts to make smart cities more accessible were mostly based on isolated measures, which were not feasible. The UD offers an environment where individuals with disabilities can participate as members of the community, and the goal of universal design is to provide accessible solutions which benefit everyone, not just persons with disabilities (Center for Universal Design, 1995; Mackett, 2020). Figure 8 depicts the principles of universal design, which comprises equitable, efficient, effective, flexible, appropriate, intuitive and tolerant.

Figure 8 depicts the principles of universal design adapted from the literature (Center for Universal Design, 1995; Kenyon et al., 2002). Universal design entails creating products and services that are usable by all, without the need for specialist design or adaptation (Kenyon et al., 2002). Thus, several European countries are adopting the UD to improve public transport facilities to help address the needs of citizens, while eliminating barriers that often limit the mobility of older people (Mackett, 2020; Park & Chowdhury, 2022). The UD approach is grounded on the concept of social inclusion, irrespective of the individual's ability. This encompasses but is not restricted to individuals with disabilities and older persons (Mackett, 2020). In urban environments, the adoption of UD measures focuses on resolving physical barriers that prevent people in terms of mobility accessibility (Center for Universal Design, 1995; World Health Organization, 2011). *But irrespective of this development, very little research has been conducted on how universal design measures can be employed to foster mobility welfare and well-being for older people, mostly those with disabilities.* The adoption of the UD principle to urban mobility infrastructure promotes usability, independence and accessibility to individuals with all ranges of abilities, from the young to even older people using wheeled devices, such as strollers and prams and older people with varying disabilities. For older people with disabilities, their mobility needs are determined by the nature and degree of their disability (Park & Chowdhury, 2022). As depicted in Figure 8, the principles of universal design can be adopted to improve the safe walkability and wayfinding of older people.

Figure 8. Principles of universal design.

4.2.5. Use of assistive devices and emerging technologies for improving mobility safety

The design of the cities mostly prevents older and disabled people from going for a walk, due to accessibility issues. These issues range from changes of steep steps level, high and poorly maintained roadways, few controlled crossing points, with busy roads, unlit bus stations/stops and inadequate seats and older people's perceptions that roads are unsafe, especially during the winter season (Kenyon et al., 2002). Therefore, cities have a substantial impact on the ease of travel made by older people. The issue of accessibility in an urban environment journey begins as soon as older people leave their residence, making it challenging for older people and those with disabilities to walk (Wazani et al., 2021). Prior studies have adopted technological assistive devices for improving walkability and wayfinding in cities, especially to support the mobility of older people with legal blindness/vision impairment. *According to this study, a model is designed based on the Human Activity Assistive Technology (HAAT) model initially proposed by Cook and Hussey (2002). The HAAT model is employed in this study as it offers a framework for the design of the general structure needed to implement technological assistive devices for improving mobility safety (Peraković et al., 2015). The HAAT model (as shown in Figure 9), not only facilitates the synthesis, analysis and development but*

also aids in the connection of the technological assistive devices, allowing users, such as older people, to perform mobility and walkability activities.

Figure 9 depicts the designed HATT model, which comprises four main components: activities, individuals, technological assistive devices and context. Table 1 describes how the HAAT model supports the safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding of older people.

Furthermore, as shown in Table 1, the components of the HAAT model can support safe mobility, reliability and wayfinding for older people. For example, technological assistive devices can help locate older pedestrians using base stations, such as Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM), Universal Mobile Telecommunications System (UMTS) and Long-Term Evolution (LTE), etc. It is recommended that Wi-Fi or wireless technology can be connected to by devices mostly used by older people, as it facilitates transfer speeds based on the standard protocols frequencies of either 2.4 GHz (802.11b and 802.11 g) or 5 GHz (802.11a) which aids data transfer speeds of about 54 Mbit/s. Also, traffic lights and mobile terminal devices have to be adapted for older persons. Researchers such as Peraković et al. (2015) recommended that RFID technology can be used to achieve more precise information of older people who walk daily along the traffic network. The RFID technology can help to identify and inform older pedestrians about the state and condition of traffic intersections when they walk within and across cities. Older pedestrians can receive real-time traffic information from *intelligent traffic control system* managed by *public traffic system control* using their handheld devices via a mobile terminal device which uses different data, such as open data, crowd-sourcing data, historical batch data, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), data transfer systems within mobile networks (General Packet Radio Service (GPRS)).

Figure 9. The HAAT model adapted from Cook and Hussey (2002).

Table 1. HAAT model to improve safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding for older people.

Components	Description
The context	Mainly comprises the environment in which the assistive technology is utilized. Thus, the context component comprises the social setting and physical surroundings in which older people who adopt the assistive technology are functioning.
Individuals	These are the end users who, in the context of this study, are the older people who require safe and sustainable mobility and walkability. The users are at the centre of the system.
Activities	Mostly involves the walkability task, procedure or work performed by older people. The whole model depends on the activities carried out by the users.
Technological assistive devices	This involve technological infrastructures that allow data transfer data, such as Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), Near-field communication (NFC), Real-time Locating Systems (RTLS), etc. to improve localization and navigation for older people (Peraković et al., 2015) that are to be used or employed to overcome the mobility and walkability barriers and hindrances in cities.

Moreover, the Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM), Enhanced Data rates for GSM Evolution (EDGE), The Universal Mobile Telecommunications System (UMTS), etc. and Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), has now been integrated with technological assistive devices to provide digital solutions for navigation and guidance information of older people in smart cities. Also, other information includes traffic information, real-time information, intersection information and Point of Interest (POI) information, which provides automated data based on real-world public location to older people through different mobile application connectivity (Anthony Jnr, 2021; Periša et al., 2015). The HAAT model focused on identifying the limitations faced when implementing technological assistive devices in urban space. Currently, fewer studies have examined the development of a safe mobility and walkability system for older people in urban areas (Bokolo, 2023b). But the mobility safety can be improved for all pedestrians via quality infrastructure and information provided, especially to older pedestrians, according to their abilities and mobility needs. Several technologies have been provided to improve the wayfinding of older people by offering personalization according to the needs of the user.

The appropriate technologies and well-designed walkability facilities can improve the safety of citizens. Portable handheld devices can inform wayfinding according to the user's needs and using appropriate interfaces for a particular group of older people, e.g. those who are visually impaired or with cognitive difficulties. In smart cities, this kind of system could also help older pedestrians with disabilities in the form of an accessible digital map to plan safer trips, perhaps avoiding complex streets or junctions with too much traffic (Marin-Lamellet-INRETS & Simoes-ISEC, 2010). However, much work is needed to enhance digital maps for older pedestrian navigation and routeing, deploying Geographic Information System (GIS), spatial computing, which provides information needed to guide the mobility and walkability of impaired pedestrians in smart cities (Jnr, 2025). As mobility is strongly linked with orientation and navigation systems/tools, GISs have been employed to provide a wide range of mobility solutions, particularly for route calculation and the integration of assistive devices (sonic or haptic) to support the transfer of information to older people (Lahav, 2014).

The deployment of GIS in the public transportation system aids multimodal routeing and navigation tasks for drivers and passengers. Finally, to support indoor mobility of older people technologies, such as Bluetooth, radio-frequency identification, or wireless

local area network, can be employed to address the lack of availability of GPS signals (GPS signals help reduce error during independent navigation and guidance (Anthony & Petersen, 2020; Periša et al., 2015)), within the buildings (Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017). Using various indicators, a classification of GIS in the context of legal blindness/vision impairment can be known. Thus, these systems can be used for navigation, routing and mobility planning and decision support tools to reduce mobility barriers and increase mobility accessibility in urban environments. Prior development has built tactile mapping, touch and haptic interfaces, such as audio-haptic and push-pin pads interfaces integrated with augmented reality to facilitate mobility of older people. Moreover, the application of cartographic representation of information, for instance, combined with acoustic and haptic information, landmarks, information about environmental conditions, accessible mobility infrastructure, etc., can improve the mobility of older people (Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017).

4.2.5.1. Emerging technologies as facilitators for safe mobility of older people. The adoption of emerging technologies can facilitate human-to-computer interaction in which technologies can be deployed to help humans adapt to the urban environment (Sobnath et al., 2020). Emerging technologies have been deployed to support the mobility of older people with special needs in society. For instance, mobile phone apps integrated with Global Positioning System (GPS) technology functionality (Anthony Jnr et al., 2021), which can help individuals with special needs navigate within and across cities and also use public transportation systems, particularly for older people with legal blindness or vision impairment. However, older people who lack access to smartphones with internet connectivity or cannot use them, may not use these technologies (Kassens-Noor et al., 2021). Prior research on the adoption of emerging technologies to support the mobility of older people has focused on proving aids for older people with legal blindness or visual impairment, mainly providing high-tech assistive devices, such as robotic aids, electronic white canes, GPS for accessibility or navigation tools from talking maps and on-trip information, as well as supported tools for virtual reality (Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017). In smart cities, emerging technologies can help to improve walkability by providing solutions, such as audible and haptic vibrotactile/feedback indicators-based augmented systems for older pedestrians, which would provide wayfinding information about their location (Sobnath et al., 2020).

Peraković et al. (2015) developed a cloud computing architecture to enable the mobility of blind people by providing important information needed for safe and coordinated walkability along the traffic network. Relevant information is provided to users using Web 2.0 technology, enabled by using Internet-enabled mobile application (Peraković et al., 2015). But due to the different perception of older people and the spatial environment, their ability to travel independently is the most significant challenge that older people face. Thus, most older people do not independently leave their place of residence, and when they are going on unassisted trips, they mostly follow known routes to avoid being lost and disorientation, as well as stress, which keeps older people from walking alone in unfamiliar districts (Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017). Furthermore, older people, mostly those who have disabilities, use a variety of assistive technologies to navigate independently. *Though several tools exist to support older people navigate, these systems are faced with many setbacks due to inadequate geographical data, insufficient*

geospatial resolution and a lack of route adaptation for mobility personalization based on different user-specific mobility criteria. Therefore, there is a need for a personalized routing system for older people to carry out their daily mobility routine activities seamlessly without any limitation (Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017).

With the increased use of smartphones, handheld devices and wearable devices, and the surge in the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI), cloud computing, Internet of Things (IoT), Big Data, wireless networks, embedded systems, Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR)/(AR), robotics, digital twins and remote sensors (Anthony Jnr & Abbas Petersen, 2021; Sobnath et al., 2020), have provided opportunities to improve the mobility of older people. With the deployment of AI-based machine learning and image recognition, the navigation of older people can be improved as objects that act as obstacles within the routes of older pedestrians can be identified. For example, in regions where the Wi-Fi network infrastructure is viable, assistive technologies can be exploited to help older people move around. These could involve smart IoT devices embedded with machine learning technologies-based image recognition that provides auditory clues to older citizens (Jnr, 2025; Sobnath et al., 2020). The use of IoT, sensors, among other digital technologies, can help to improve the mobility of older people, allowing them to detect obstacles outdoors and indoors so that older people with disabilities can benefit from integration and full inclusion in society (Sobnath et al., 2020). Through the use of AI, and data mining, IoT of connected to physical devices using short communication coverage, such as Bluetooth, Real-time locating system (RTLS), WiFi, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) and Near-field communication (NFC), the independent and safe mobility of older people can be improved (Bokolo, 2023b; Jnr, 2025). Emerging technologies, such as IoT, can support communication connectivity for older people with other public transportation systems within the surrounding urban.

The convergence of these emerging technologies can provide a notable cluster of opportunities and functionalities, which can support the mobility of older people in smart cities (Sobnath et al., 2020). The technology convergence of Big Data, AI and IoT can contribute to increasing safe mobility for older people by increasing the overall road/pedestrian accessibility. The use of emerging technologies such as VR/AR can improve the mobility ability of older people with physical, sensorial, learning and mental disabilities (Bokolo et al., 2022; Lahav, 2014). AI can increase the autonomy for older people and can be used to support walkability and wayfinding for the visually impaired in navigating cities (Jnr, 2025; Kassens-Noor et al., 2021). However, the implementation and use of AI is still subject to a myriad of ethical debates due to issues raised from privacy, security, bias, etc. Big Data, AI and IoT can be applied to present personalized information to aid the daily needs and mobility of older people, for example, providing personalized directions and avoiding barriers for improved walkability and wayfinding. This information provided can be used for pre-trip planning via a user-centered accessible and designed interface which provides customized mobility information in a clear, simple and easy way. Older people who will use such systems may not have prior knowledge of Geographic Information System (GIS), only understanding how navigation works on handheld devices. This system will help with movement, orientation and wayfinding for older people who rely on their olfactory, kinesthetic, tactile and auditory senses (Zimmermann-Janschitz et al., 2017).

4.2.5.2. Use of AI-based machine learning tools for safe walkability of older people. A navigation and route guidance system, which can be integrated in older people's mobile phones or handheld devices, can aid accessibility, for example, to support an older pedestrian with legal blindness/vision impairment to navigate from one point to another on foot. He/she can utilize the pedestrian route guidance system by pre-setting the start or origin point and destination or end point in the system using the adapted Human Machine Interface (HMI), when the individual starts walking (Jnr, 2025). Close to every crossroad, the system notifies the pedestrian when it is safe to walk and uses tactile pavement to stay on the right trajectory when crossing the street. After some pre-defined centimetres, the navigation system informs the older pedestrian that he/she is arriving at a shared public space and advises the individual to use the tactile pavement (Marin-Lamellet-INRETS & Simoes-ISEC, 2010). Accordingly, use of these digital tools for navigation can improve older people's ability to adjust and cope with mobility changes due to old age. This can help to foster a sense of mastery for older people's mobility needs, where the 'sense of mastery' in psychological studies involves an individual's ability to manage life conditions in relation to the control of one's life (Siren et al., 2015). Particularly, the use of digital tools can improve mobility towards greater independence and autonomy for older people's daily mobility needs (Völkel & Weber, 2008).

Furthermore, Electronic Travel Aids (ETAs) have previously been developed and mainly used targeting mobility accessibility problems for people with disabilities, aimed at supporting location and orientation information, obstacle avoidance systems and optimal route computations during navigation. Although the current system is faced with limitations such as the current ETAs not being user-centred, resulting in a series of interaction and usability issues, not providing the best travel guidance to users, mostly people with legal blindness/vision impairment, thus making walkability difficult for the users. This was due to the medium by which information was presented to the users. As relevant information is not provided to users in a way that it can oriented and useful. This information occasionally overwhelms the users as a huge amount of information is provided (Sochor, 2015). As such, users are forced to access Mobility and Orientation (M&O) information using their remaining senses, which was achieved by physical devices that provided multimedia features, such as audio/sound and haptic interfaces. Therefore, there is a need for devices that provide information that commuters cannot obtain on their own. This also necessitates that ETAs as M&O aids should improve their autonomy and help users with legal blindness/vision impairment to be more independent when walking in cities. *Therefore, ETAs should make navigation and wayfinding easier and not demanding.* This means that the use of digital devices should aid the acquisition and development of M&O abilities, not replacing the involved human processes. The objective is to improve the independent navigation of individuals with legal blindness/vision impairment via the use of handheld devices. The role that a digital device can play in navigation should reduce as the user develops more M&O skills and tactics (Sochor, 2015).

However it was highlighted that the use of these navigation systems could overload pedestrians and possibly increase the risk of injury for older people when they walk or cross a street. Thus, there is a need for studies to examine how to provide information to older pedestrians to mitigate negative risk effects (Marin-Lamellet-INRETS &

Simoes-ISEC, 2010). Moreover, any slight incompatibility or variation with reality or urban space will decrease an individual's trust in navigation systems and possibly lead to potential injury. Another challenge in the design and development of digital tools, such as maps, includes the provision of different interfaces. This is based on the sensorial limitations of older people, processing time for the portable system to run. While older people are walking or crossing a pedestrian area, the provision of an emergency button facilitates fast connection via an emergency service, which provides the location of older people in case of an emergency (Marin-Lamellet-INRETS & Simoes-ISEC, 2010). From the developers' point of view, the lack of detailed data about features of the roads, routes and walkways, such as surface conditions of sidewalks or road incline, limits developers from obtaining routeing networks information tailored for older people (Mayordomo-Martínez et al., 2019).

Thus, AI-based machine learning algorithms, based on collaboratively collected geodata and open data, can help to generate personalized routes, especially for older people with disabilities. The AI tool collects important data needed to define older pedestrians' requests, which are categorized based on *basic information*, as shown in Figure 10 supported by the adoption of current mobility aids, whereas *expanded information*, as presented in Figure 11 involves additional information provided using technological assistive devices. The basic individuals' requests data comprise the parameters shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 depicts the basic individuals' requests as data needed to support the safe mobility and walkability of older people in smart cities. These data sources can be used by the AI-based ML systems.

Figure 11 shows the expanded information, which captures the older people's requests supported by technological assistive devices and services. Moreover, for designing machine learning-based image recognition support systems, it is essential to involve older people in the design process themselves. Such an approach will enable developers

Figure 10. AI-based ML for safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding of older people.

to customize the digital system design that would suit the mobility needs and requirements (Sobnath et al., 2020). Furthermore, when providing audible pedestrian suggestions, developers should consider some critical features that affect disabled older pedestrians, such as users with legal blindness/vision impairment who, at times, will listen to traffic sound coming from adjacent travel lanes to know when they should cross. But this may be challenging as new vehicles, such as hybrid and electric vehicles, generate less noise. Also, if the volume level of the audible pedestrian navigation system is too loud, this will distract older pedestrian with legal blindness/vision impairment as they may not be able to visibly hear other audible clues (e.g. sound of the chirp, construction sound, etc.) that they are used to when they cross or walk in road intersection.

To address this constraint, navigation systems that allow for adapting the application volume linked to the background ambient noise level. Marin-Lamellet-INRETS and Simoes-ISEC (2010) suggested providing a vibratory indication that offers information about where the button is located at a road cross along a street, where the WALK signal is on. Thus, the use of integrated or external GPS receivers' application which enables navigation and guidance of users via Real-time Locating System (RTLs) tag (Periša et al., 2015), can aid in improving the walkability and movement of older

Figure 11. Expanded information for safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding for older people.

people (Jnr, 2025). Technologies, such as GPS, NFC, Bluetooth, RFID, WiFi or RTLS, can be used that enable the user to receive accurate information about their position (Peraković et al., 2015). This information is obtained from the digital system based on the location of the individual and is provided in the form of voice or audio information. The digital system then navigates older people using voice information or tactile information for those with legal blindness/vision impairment. After the authentication of the user, the system allows actuation (which is the condition or state of being moved or impelled to action), of the audio motioning contributes to safe mobility and orientation of older people based on the noise produced by the audio signalling infrastructure at traffic intersections.

Moreover, the availability of real-time data for the user, as seen in Figure 10, informs older pedestrians with voice or audio information about alternative routes for safe walkability in case of road closure or inaccessible pedestrian crossing due to road construction. Using AI-based machine learning, the navigation system can provide walkability information which includes the suggestion of the shortest route, provision of built environment information regarding the user environment and pre-information when approaching their destination. In an urban environment more information that improves the safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding includes the provision of information on the direction of tactile for better accessibility using voice information provided to individuals comprising the size of the intersection, related elements (such as the number of available lanes in which direction), existence of bus/train and tram stops (Peraković et al., 2015).

4.3. Case studies of urban mobility policies for older people

The public transportation system typically comprises buses, local trains, trams and metro, which is mostly supplemented with various facilitated mobility services for older and disabled people, e.g. paratransit services (Levin et al., 2012). Presently, it is important to investigate and understand the use of paratransit services, whether it has become a travel mode for older people only when traditional public transportation service is unavailable and/or whether it supplements or replaces other forms of public transportation (Mercado et al., 2010). Researchers such as Mercado et al. (2010) mentioned that the current physical condition and changing mobility lifestyles of older people make the traditional public transportation, which is based on fixed-route transit, challenging for older people. As such, some older people refer to using paratransit services such as dial-a-ride, which offers greater flexibility and particularly adapted vehicles that facilitate convenience and usage (Abir & Hoque, 2011; Mercado et al., 2010).

In Norway, the Norwegian Ministry of Transport (Anthony Jnr, 2024), The National Transport Plan 2022–2033' was proposed. The plan presented policies and urgencies within an economic, technological, social and technological framework for twelve years and provides perspectives toward transport 2050. Also, in Norway, a Special Transport Services (STS) known as 'TT-ordningen' (Norwegian: tilrettelagt transport), which is a demand-responsive door-to-door mobility service and/or more personal assistance is provided to older people and individuals with severe functional limitations and those with disabilities who cannot use ordinary public transportation. The STS is mainly operated with multi-purpose vehicles or taxi-cars (Levin et al., 2012), provided by

municipalities and transport companies. The STS provides mobility services from older people's residences, nursing homes and day care centres (Levin et al., 2012). In Norway, the county councils (Norwegian: fylkeskommunene) are required to organize STS adapted for older and disabled people (Solvoll, 2010). The permits for the STS are provided by municipalities to those who are eligible for the support (for mobility impairment (Norwegian: for flytning shemming)).

In most county councils, the STS is organized in the form of a door-to-door taxi services with variations in how STS is planned between county councils; for instance, as related to the number people qualified to receive the support, the degree to which they may utilize it and the frequency of journey allowed to a particular commuter (Solvoll, 2010). Usually, the STS is provided to individuals in the form of electronic coupons or value cards with a specified number of trips. In 2010, it was recorded that about 100,000 permits were issued for the STS in Norway, compared to 7,300 in 2009 and 6,400 in 2008. But often, some of those qualified to use the STS do not use it due to reduced mobility or users not actively travelling due to several reasons (Solvoll, 2010). The specialized transport service is implemented as multi-purpose vehicles, mini-buses or taxi services (Ruter, 2017; Sparelabs, 2019). Also, in Norway, 5% of everyday trips by age group 67–74 years in 2009 were covered by public transportation services. Nonetheless, the differences in these results between and within countries are often due to the provision of facilitated transport services for older and disabled people (Levin et al., 2012). In general, the use of normal public transportation services is quite low among older people. This is consistent with findings from Sweden, which revealed that about 40% of the older populace do not utilize public transportation at all, and almost 5% of the daily trips among older people in 2000 were covered by public transportation, whereas 60% of the trips were covered by car (Levin et al., 2012). In the United Kingdom (UK), the provision of concessionary transit (bus) fares, which offer a reduced fare or, most time, a free option for older people in the population, can increase the use of public transportation and reduce reliance on personal car ownership (Mercado et al., 2010).

In the United States of America (USA), about 12 per cent of the population utilized dial-a-ride specialized transportation services. The users of these services comprise individuals with medical conditions that affect their mobility. In British Columbia, Canada, a study among Caucasian educated older population stated that the utilization of specialized transit services has been associated with first existing social networks of older people, which serve to encourage and inform the older populations in the use of these specialized transit services. Secondly, among chronically ill older people, their knowledge, and thirdly, their perception of the specialized transit services benefits (Mercado et al., 2010). Mercado et al. (2010) highlighted about 73 specialized transit services were deployed in the urban areas of Ontario, Canada in 2004 for older people who could not use standard public transportation systems due to disability and mobility impairment. These mobility services respond to individualized mobility requests for better mobility services operated via dial-a-ride services provided by the municipalities. Moreover, there are difficulties as most users need to plan and make travel reservations in advance and are not given much flexibility in making trip changes as reservations need to be done 4–5 days ahead. Also, there have been complaints about the quality of mobility service, including inconsiderate and at times rude drivers. There is a need for

these issues to be investigated further for recommendations to improve the current public transportation service and infrastructure but also in improving operational management of the entire transit system in smart cities (Mercado et al., 2010).

5. Discussion and implications of the study

5.1. Discussion

This study examines the use of emerging technologies and universal design measures to improve the safe walkability and wayfinding of older people, which can be a radical force to change urban mobility design process, toward meeting the diverse mobility needs of existing and future residents and contributing to improving their quality of life. Hjorthol (2013) stated that most older groups face difficulty in using public transportation due to issues faced when they walk or because of inaccessible public transportation. For cities to ease the use of public transportation alternatives, it is suggested to deploy initiatives to improve mobility accessibility of city buses by the provision of ramps, low-floor buses, raising and extending sidewalks at bus stations/stops, etc. Additional recommendations include improvements to older people's security at bus stations/stops, provision of route and trip information, restructuring of routes suitable to older travellers, offering training to drivers and using safer and accessible vehicles (Oxley et al., 2010). Oxley et al. (2010) also advocated for the provision of alternative mobility options, often referred to as Supplemental Transportation Programs (STPs), for older people who are unable to drive or use public transportation.

In the USA, a range of STPs is provided to older people either as door-to-door mobility services or a higher level of assistance termed as door-to-door transportation or assisted mobility services. Overall, these customized door-to-door mobility services are typically tailored to specific community needs and offer hands-on trip assistance when older people enter and exit the vehicle, as well as while travelling in the vehicle. These services are apparently highly useful for older people with disabilities, most often when they go for medical appointments and other community activities (Oxley et al., 2010). These customized door-to-door mobility services are also employed in Norway as Special Transport Services (STS) (Levin et al., 2012; Solvoll, 2010). Hjorthol, 2013) suggested that it is important that the welfare dimension is considered when providing public transportation for the older population. The literature indicated that older people do not use public transportation compared to other groups in society. At times, the STS provided by the municipalities and other mobility service providers is not well publicized among the older people groups (Hjorthol, 2013). The result further pointed out that the STPs provided by the local authorities are perceived by older people as insufficient (Hjorthol, 2013).

In the UK, the provision of concessionary transit (bus) fares, which offer a reduced fare or, most time free option for older people (Mercado et al., 2010). In *Ontario, Canada*, it is offered as specialized transit services operated via dial-a-ride services provided by the municipalities (Mercado et al., 2010). Moreover, data sources, such as geospatial data, regarding accessible public facilities for pre-trip planning, were perceived as useful for older people, especially for older people (Sze & Christensen, 2017). For instance, a safe pedestrian environment and a high level of public transportation service were found essential to older people. The perceived environment, security and safety also impact

trip characteristics in relation to mobility mode, trip frequency and trip time of older people (Sze & Christensen, 2017). A study in Norway mentioned that limited accessibility during the winter season limits the walkability and mobility of older people. The findings from the study argued for comprehensive planning of walking and pedestrian routes, particularly during the winter season, to provide informed information of paths without snow clearing that are difficult to walk. The participants suggested employing a holistic perspective on maintaining pedestrian routes during winter, especially across the retirement homes and home care centres. The older people communicated the importance of mobility accessibility and that public facilities to rest along the public space can result in good health, well-being and coping (Krogstad et al., 2015). The effective management and maintenance of the pedestrian walkway or footpath, bus stop, accessible route and the surrounding urban environment are essential to improve safe mobility.

5.2. Implications for practice and society

During the last decade, the use of emerging technologies and technological assistive devices has evolved to support the mobility, walkability and wayfinding of older people. Also, the mobility needs of older people in the context of their mobility behaviour, including orientation features, barriers, landmarks and obstacles or Points of Interest (POIs) have not been well covered in the literature. *Although many devices and digital platforms have been developed, little work has focused on employing emerging technologies such as AI-based machine learning to improve safe walkability and wayfinding for older people by considering the different, variable and special spatial state of cities.* Lahav (2014) stated that there is a need to improve the orientation and mobility for older people, especially in outdoor environments and complex public spaces. Also, it is required to maintain a balance between haptic and audio representations while ensuring that the system is user-friendly and adapted for the needs of older people, for example, information should be provided to zoom in and zoom out landmarks or get more information about objects in local spaces (Lahav, 2014).

AI-based machine learning can receive real-time bus scheduling, suggest best routes for their journeys and provide convenient tools such as audio interface which provides verbal wayfinding information regarding routes and obstacles as well as the Point of Interest (POI) (e.g. coffee shops, pharmacies, restaurants, shopping markets), to support multimodal user-friendly interface. Also, the use of crowdsourcing data and Google Street View (GSV) can help older people with information for walkability and wayfinding of older people when they navigate new surroundings. Crowdsourcing data can also be exploited to develop mobility solutions for older people with legal blindness/vision impairment in navigating around smart cities. This could aid older people in locating landmarks within the city (Sobnath et al., 2020). The crowdsourcing data from the community can be used by municipalities to help in carrying out participatory planning with the city. These data can also help to support citizen reporting, open government and support the co-creation and co-design of smart cities. The use of crowdsourcing data not only relates to technological inventions but also focuses on fostering collaborative community participation that creates innovative ideas, increases productivity while reducing the use of resources. Overall, crowdsourcing data can be employed to provide a reliable guide for older people in real time using different

directional arrow keys signalling left, right, stop or forward, which is then converted to audible instructions to individuals (Sobnath et al., 2020).

Pinto et al. (2020) stated that the provision of a mobility application for older people that predicts bus arrival, schedules and routes and with accessibility features for individuals with legal blindness/vision impairment. This allows older people to express their mobility interest in advance before the arrival of public transportation, such as city buses when boarding by sending information which appears to the bus driver as a message. This information is displayed to the bus driver and appears on the vehicle control panel of the selected bus line. With such information, the bus driver can provide any mobility support needed by the individuals at the particular bus stop/station in advance or when he/she is picking up the individuals. This study suggests the use of emerging technologies such as AI-based machine learning using different data sources to personalized walkability based on the personal needs of the individuals, and further assess the older people's ability to apply this new spatial knowledge in real-life scenarios. For example, using open data sources, such as textual data about the urban environment, maps, photos can be employed in machine learning and image recognition to supports mobility and walkability accessible such as information provision for routes access, signage, entrances, elevators, kerb ramps, corridors, doors, ramps and toilets (Mayordomo-Martínez et al., 2019). Although Mayordomo-Martínez et al. (2019) argued that the use of textual information might not display important details which are illustrated in an image.

Moreover, a study revealed that people can categorize visual information faster than using words. These features can make it simpler for older people with disabilities to recognize mobility access that best fits their travel needs (Mayordomo-Martínez et al., 2019). On the other hand, crowdsourcing data and data from social networks can be used to capture the structural features of cities, such as routes and junctions, to improve mobility accessibility and offer mobility connections to older people. Generally, older people with special needs have unique mobility needs and thereby face considerable barriers in accessing essential public services and achieving an independent life (Kassens-Noor et al., 2021). Therefore, this study advocates for the use of emerging technologies such as machine learning that enables older people to plan their daily journeys using seamless private and public transportation modes that offer seamless connection of existing mobility services and the creation of others, such as specialized or flexible transport modes for older people. This can also offer personalized navigation (in relation to the particular mobility needs of the user, i.e. type and degree of disability, available facilities of fitted system, etc.), which enables the mobility of impaired individuals to leverage real-time data to guide available public transportation. The use of emerging technologies can support urban administration or city transit operators by providing data sources in different formats in interoperable and standardized data formats to be leveraged for improving urban traffic management to enhance the mobility experience of older people in a way that offers a valuable mobility tool to them.

5.3. Implications for research and policy

Universally, socially disadvantaged older people, especially those living with disability, are among those at increased risk of pedestrian and road traffic risk and injuries. Also, the ageing population are often overlooked in road planning, road safety research and

transport policy development. The mobility needs and accessibility requirements of older people must be better understood by municipalities and policymakers to ensure that transport administrations, in particular, direct the right resources to support the mobility and walkability of the ageing population in a way that improves public transportation services. The ageing population in the society comprises a heterogeneous group (65–74 and 75 and older), a variety of mobility accessibility options (for disabled and non-disabled) (Bokolo, 2023b). Thus, different mobility modes will be desirable, and this must be recognized as there are differences between the travel patterns and needs of each group. Therefore, understanding the mobility needs and travel patterns of these different groups of older people, which include ‘65–74’ to the oldest old ‘75 and older’, especially those over 80 years who will need mobility support, will be a challenge for transport planning and traffic authorities. Prior studies have attempted to deploy measures aimed at improving older people’s mobility in accordance with different mobility modes (Jnr, 2025). However, fewer studies have been conducted that explore measures that can improve safe mobility, walkability and wayfinding for older people.

Much of the prior studies on mobility of older people are more concentrated on exploring the mapping of the travel behaviour of the older population (Levin et al., 2012). Nonetheless, in the Scandinavian countries, limited research has been carried out regarding how to improve the walkability and mobility of the ageing population. Accordingly, there is a need for research that improves mobility accessibility and safety in public transportation, based on better legislation, policies and monitoring. Implications from this study advance the literature on the understanding of different mobility needs of the older populations by providing decision support to policymakers in developing inclusive, safe and sustainable urban policies. This study provides an up-to-date overview of best practices, such as practical measures promoting safe mobility of older people. The study highlights the need for more practice-based policy research to better inform about the safety risks among older people. This article will provide inspiration and guidance in the development of strategies that support older people’s mobility, and at the same time identify gaps and needs for further research and planning of development. This study highlights the use of paratransit services to meet the varying mobility needs of older people to avoid social isolation and improve their quality of life.

In line with Mercado et al., 2010, this study expanded on the diversity of older people and underlined the need to secure public transportation options for the ageing population to be independently mobile, thereby contributing to their welfare and well-being. The findings propose the need for policies to establish an inclusive action plan towards an age and disability-friendly public transportation environment. Ensuring that older people and those living with disability have a safe and accessible urban mobility system for the ageing population. In addition, urban policies should be directed to safeguard the privacy of older people. These policies should be created on ‘Privacy by Design’ measures throughout the development lifecycle of the AI-based machine learning systems. Data processors and controllers must be active in addressing possible data security and privacy implications in the use of personalized data of older people. As such, sensitive personal information, such as health data of older people, should only be collected and used under explicit consent either from the older people, family members, caregivers, care home departments or municipalities. Processing of personal data without consent is not to be allowed under any circumstances, and data access to

personal health or social information is to be limited by applications whose permissions have been authorized in compliance with the Equality Act 2010. An electronic consent (eConsent) might be employed to collect consent from a designated person on behalf of the older adult.

6. Conclusion, limitations and future research

Sustainable and safe public transportation is a key factor for accessing essential public services and resources, including social welfare and well-being. However, evidence from the literature suggests that mobility of older people is still an under-researched area. The goal to address the mobility and walkability needs and requirements of an ageing society still has several questions that need answers (Levin et al., 2012). One aspect of older people that has received little consideration is the mobility safety challenge faced by older people. Therefore, municipalities are still faced with limitations in understanding the mobility safety demands of older people, both those with and without disabilities and in executing appropriate sustainable mobility measures for society. This review study suggests that the adoption of universal design measures could enable safe mobility, walkability, and provide new accessibility, to address the limitations of technological assistive devices, and increase the physical mobility of older people based on a literature review of existing studies. Given advances in emerging technologies, such as AI, big data, machine learning, etc., it is important to enhance the availability of accessible public transportation facilities for personalized pre-trip planning and real-time navigation, to improve the safe mobility and walkability of older people using different data sources.

Accordingly, in this study, a model is designed based on the Human Activity Assistive Technology (HAAT) model. Also, this study examines how universal design measures and the use of emerging technologies such as AI-based machine learning can improve safe walkability and wayfinding. Evidence from this study can contribute to understanding the mobility of older people by considering the conventional use of public transportation (mobility), but also the passive movement of older pedestrians using non-transportation means (walkability). Nevertheless, a limitation of this study is that only secondary data were employed. In future, mixed-mode methodology will be employed, and data will be collected using focus group interviews with older people and public transportation providers. Furthermore, primary data will be collected using a survey questionnaire from older people, their caregivers and urban mobility providers to provide more insights on how to achieve safe mobility for older people. The collected data will be analysed using statistical tools such as SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for quantitative data analysis.

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